

ECOBULK

D8.4: A summary of tools developed through ECOBULK

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About ECOBULK and this document

ECOBULK was delivered by the work of 26 partners and is focused on the construction, automotive and furniture sectors. The project considered all aspects of a product's lifecycle and how and where improvements could be made to increase the circularity of product. This included design, circular materials, component manufacture, product use, product life extension and materials recovery and testing circular business models. Details of aspects of ECOBULK linked to these lifecycle steps are shown overleaf.

As part of the project, tools were developed both as an explicit objective of ECOBULK, and in supporting the delivery of project objectives. A summary of these tools is provided here.

ECOBULK: an overview of areas of focus

CIRCULAR PROTOTYPE DESIGN

- Modular furniture
- Vehicle parts designed for disassembly
- Outdoor structures designed for disassembly
- Consideration of different business models supported by design

CIRCULAR MATERIALS

- FRP composites using biobased and recycled raw materials
- Characterisation of materials
- Low formaldehyde binders
- Use of waste products as a raw material

COMPONENT MANUFACTURE

- Component moulding and extrusion using new materials
- Fasteners to support disassembly

PRODUCT USE

- Validation tests (eg weight, aesthetics, heat ageing etc) of components
- User acceptance tests
- Deployment in vehicles
- Testing of different business models (e.g. financial modelling)

PRODUCT LIFE EXTENSION

- Dismantling and disassembly testing

MATERIAL RECOVERY

- Material recyclability tests of demonstration components
- Recovery of plastics from ASR

Material and Manufacturing Technology Selection (WP2)

Objective of the tool:

The Ansys Granta Selector tool enables the selection of materials and processes following criteria for:

- Technical performance (e.g. FAA approved, coatings, ...)
- Environmental impact (CO₂, Energy, Waste, Water, ...)
- Supply chain risk (restricted substances, legislations, critical materials, ...)
- End-of-life options and environmental impact
- Cost for materials and manufacturing
- And more!

The tool is supported by several material and manufacturing specific datasets, and MaterialUniverse™ containing over 4000 commercial available engineering materials.

Use within ECOBULK:

The tool and datasets were used to support benchmark social, environmental and economic performance of case study parts. You can learn more about the tool and datasets at:

<https://www.ansys.com/products/materials/granta-selector>

<https://www.ansys.com/products/materials/materials-data-library>

Further Information: Donna.Dykeman@ansys.com

Circular design framework for composite products (WP2)

Objective of the tool:

The circular design framework connects Circular strategies, such as reuse and recycling, to design aspects like connection & materials selection, supporting design for a circular economy.

Use within ECOBULK:

The framework was used to analyse the products to support thinking around the design of composite products.

Ecobulk report D2.2 final and the associated design guide provide a comprehensive overview of design strategies, design guidelines and examples from demonstrator development.

For further information please contact Jelle Joustra at:
j.j.joustra@tudelft.nl

Circular strategies

Design aim	Product integrity			Materials integrity		
	Circular strategy	Long life	Lifetime extension	Product recovery	Structural reuse	Material recycling
Concept design						
Accessibility		● ●	●			● ●
Adaptability	●	● ● ●	● ●		●	
Cleanability	● ●	● ● ●	●			●
Dis-&reassembly	●	● ● ●	● ● ●		●	● ●
Ergonomics	● ●	● ● ●	●			
Fault isolation	● ●	● ● ●	●			●
Functional packaging		●	●			●
Interchangeability		● ● ●	● ● ●		●	●
Malfunction signalling	●	●	●			
Simplification	● ●	● ● ●	● ●			●
Embodiment						
Connection selection	● ●	● ● ●	● ● ●		●	● ●
Function integration	●	● ● ●	●			● ●
Keying		● ● ●	●			
Material selection	● ●	● ● ●	● ● ●		●	● ● ●
Manufacturing		● ● ●	● ● ●			● ●
Modularity		● ● ●	● ● ●		●	● ●
Redundancy	●	● ● ●	●			
Sacrificial elements	● ●	● ● ●	● ● ●			●
Structural design	● ● ●	● ● ●	● ● ●		●	● ●
Surface treatments	● ●	● ● ●	● ● ●			● ● ●
Detail design						
Identification		● ● ●	● ● ●		●	● ●
Monitoring	● ●	● ● ●	● ● ●			● ●
Standardisation		● ● ●	● ● ●		●	● ●
Circular storytelling			● ● ●			● ●
Timing & planning		● ●	● ●			● ●

Connection and fastener toolbox (WP2)

Objective of the tool:

The Ecobulk Fastener Finder is a web-app helping you to select from an infinite number of fasteners, based on:

- Circularity score
- (dis)assembly time
- Recycling material compatibility
- Lifecycle costing
- And more!

Use within ECOBULK:

The tool box was developed as part of the ECOBULK project.

You can access the connection and fastener toolbox at:

<http://www.bramvandergrinten.nl/ff/>

Password: Ecobulk

The screenshot shows the 'fastener finder' interface. It features a sidebar on the left with a 'use the wizard' button, an 'Apply filters' button, and dropdown menus for 'Design requirements', 'Fastener type', and 'Repair, remanufacture and recycling'. The main area has a 'Show / hide fastener data by column:' section with various filter buttons like 'Image', 'Type', 'Category', 'Description', 'Drive', 'Material', 'Ø or width', 'Shear load (kN)', 'Circularity', 'Not circular because', 'recycles with', 'Approx. price (€)', 'Lifecycle cost', 'Fastening action', 'Assembly', 'Repair time (s)', 'Reman time (s)', 'Toolspace A', 'Toolspace B', and 'Thread length'. Below this is a search bar and a table of results.

Image	Type	Description	Material	Ø or width (mm)	
Bolts					
	Bolts	Hex Bolts Ø4 x 10	Standard carbon steel	4	
	Bolts	Hex Bolts Ø4 x 10	PA6 Nylon	4	
	Bolts	Wing Bolts Ø4 x 10	Standard carbon steel	4	
	Bolts	Wing Bolts Ø4 x 10	PA6 Nylon	4	
	Bolts	Phillips Cap bolts Ø4 x 10	Standard carbon steel	4	
	Bolts	Phillips Cap bolts Ø4 x 10	PA6 Nylon	4	
	Bolts	Hex Flange bolts Ø4 x 10	Standard carbon steel	4	

Screenshot from the tool showing an example of the information contained

End-user and Stakeholder Platform Development and Implementation (WP6)

Objective of the tool:

The Ansys Granta MI Materials Information Management System enables FAIR data management and full traceability of materials, processes and products, and use of data across enterprise digital environments for decision-making, design, modelling and simulation, and advanced analytics:

- Tools to manage in-house and/or publicly procured materials data
- Comprehensive library of materials information
- Identify restricted substances
- Select compliant and sustainable materials
- De-risk designs, fulfil reporting obligations
- Integrate with CAD, CAE, PLM
- Interfaces for exploring data, screening substances, advanced analytics

Use within ECOBULK:

The tool was used to support partner demonstration for a platform to support supply chain traceability for the secondary materials and parts market. The tool is primarily used for in-house materials and information management, and as such we envision that Ansys clients can use the schemas and data curated for management and selection of secondary materials and products for their designs.

<https://www.ansys.com/products/materials/granta-mi>

See Ansys Granta MI Restricted Substances module

Further Information: Donna.Dykeman@ansys.com

Control access and distribution of materials data

Access reference data on, CO2 and energy consumption, end of life and critical materials

Import Suppliers data

Store and manage your materials data in a searchable customized database

Report on the presence of restricted substances use

Product circularity assessment methodology (WP8)

Objective of the tool:

Review of a product to understand why it was circular and to question if it could be ‘more circular’

Use case:

- Product focused
- Identify exemplar products
- Competitor analysis
- Define baseline value chain
- Hotspot identification
- Basis for action planning to increase product circularity

Use within ECOBULK:

This tool was developed within ECOBULK to enable analysis and challenge of the demonstration products against the principles of the circular economy and to feed into business model discussions.

Principle 2: Optimise resource yields through circulation	Current product related activities and performance	Potential for exploration within ECOBULK – Y/N
Prolong		
Upgrade		

Principle 1: Preserve and enhance natural capital flows	Current product related activities and performance	Potential to increase circularity
Use secondary raw materials		
Material substitution		
Use of renewable raw materials		
Etc		

Product	Circular economy principle 1: Preserve and enhance natural capital by controlling finite stocks and balancing renewable resource flows				
	Use of SRMs	Material Substitution	Use of renewable raw materials	Virtualise	Restore Regenerate
Product 1					
Product 2					
etc					

Areas for potential improvement

Areas of current activity and good practice

Not relevant

For further information please contact: info@oakdenehollins.com

Business model capability assessment tool (WP8)

Objective of the tool:

To support the analysis of business needs for the delivery of circular business strategies

Use case:

- Support with consideration of business models that could support and maximise the circular design feature of the product
- Analysis of key business changes needed to support the piloting of new business models within an existing organisation

Use within ECOBULK:

This tool was developed to support the analysis of business changes required for the introduction of new circular economy business models into existing businesses. It was developed in particular to support discussion, analysis and planning within SME's. It was used to consider the potential resource implications for the furniture demonstrator within ECOBULK

Company name:					
Provide a brief overview of the challenge to be met or opportunity identified:					
Provide brief description of the business model:					
How will revenue be earned:					
Chosen business model (see Tab B for summary of model types):	Retained ownership eg leasing				
Business capabilities needed for business model delivery	Is the capability relevant for the suggested business model	Current readiness within company	Level of investment needed to implement	Strategic significance to business model delivery	Please note key areas of focus or support need
Sourcing of different raw materials (e.g. secondary raw materials, biobased or other)	Yes - complete columns C-I	Medium	Low	High	
Redesign of products (including reformulation of products)					
Redesign of manufacturing processes (e.g. different processes needed)					
Development of new technology requirements (e.g. IoT, blockchain, product tracking abilities)					
New partnerships needed					
New employee skills to be developed (e.g. customer relations, remanufacturing)					
Change of corporate policies, culture and incentive schemes					
Different logistics requirements needed					
Legal issues (e.g. new contacts) required					
Different cash flow model required					
Consideration of mechanisms for product take back					
Engagement with investors					
Development of new business metrics					
Application of different accounting techniques (e.g. for leased assets)					
Valuation of end of life assets					
New/different channels to market needed (e.g. sell to different customer segments)					
Different customer segments for products to be accessed					
More information needed (e.g. market information)					

Financial modelling for value retention business models (WP8)

Objective of the tool:

Modelling of economic implications of the value retention business model strategy for Microcab.

Use case:

Analysis of costs and revenues for circular business models. Identification of the costs associated with the chosen value retention strategy for each automotive component part (eg for remanufacture, replacement, repair, recycling etc) to support product life extension strategy of the full life leasing models

Use within ECOBULK:

Analysis of the value retention of component parts and product life extension strategies for the financial analysis of Microcabs business model

Component	Component lifetime	Component Criticality	Relative Value	Order of VRP
Top of Dashboard	5	0.5	0.001393566	0.000696783
Steering Wheel Cover	3.5	0.5	0.000348392	0.000174196
Seating Cover	3.5	0.5	0.001161305	0.000580653
Switch Panel	3.5	1	0.000464522	0.000464522
Door Cards	7	1	0.003716177	0.003716177
etc				

Data capture for Microcab and comparators

Analysis of full life costing

For further information please contact: info@oakdenhollins.com

Material flow modelling of composites from wind turbine blades (WP8)

Objective of the tool:

Modelling the installations and decommissioning of wind turbines in Europe to 2050 to understand the likely arisings of composite waste from turbine blades.

Use case:

- Identifying the value retention opportunity and implications for waste management operations of the scale up of wind power installations in Europe.
- Assessing the scale of the environmental impacts from the use of composites within wind energy installations.
- Aiding in future analysis of embodied material flows within wind turbine installations.

Use within ECOBULK:

Used to model composite blade waste arisings in the EU28 out to 2050 and to sense check existing projections.

Blade composites arisings from decommissioning

New installed capacity (MW)

For further information please contact: info@oakdenhollins.com